

Generation of Synthetic Load Profiles of Electric Vehicles Based on Household Activity Profiles

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ABSTRACT

Sensible numerical simulations require accurate modelling as well as a framework of realistic input data as model backbone. As one component of a comprehensive simulation environment for power systems including e-mobility, this paper describes a sociologically backed approach to an e-vehicle charging load profile generator based on an existing activity-based household load generator, an extensive mobility behaviour report, and state of the art charging technology. A smart grid use case with a simple control algorithm then helps demonstrate the application of such profiles.

KEYWORDS

E-Mobility, Smart Grid Applications, Power System Simulation, Load Profile, Behavioural Modelling, Grid Controls

INTRODUCTION

The increasing share of e-mobility is a major challenge for distribution network operators. The substantial power demand of electric vehicle charging stations will increase the load in low-voltage grids in the future. In order to avoid grid overload, distribution system operators must develop suitable Smart Grid technology. Their development requires elaborate simulation environments which in turn create a need for realistic charging profiles of electric vehicles as a basis. This paper presents a sociologically accurate e-vehicle charging load profile generator.

STATE OF THE ART

There are existing approaches to creating load profiles for electrical vehicles. Work [1] is a very simple and robust approach to creating such profiles using a Weibull distribution for start and duration of the daily charging process of each vehicle. Such an algorithm can be used in the drafting phase of creating a simulation system or if the influence of its accuracy on the simulation outcome is deemed low. Another paper [2] uses three types of activity (work, shopping, leisure) and according data regarding the activity's departure time and the distance travelled. It then derives a stochastic distribution from this data much like work [1]. [3], [4] A very recent study uses a detailed study of the German Federal Motor Transport Authority to derive load profiles which are later added to an existing household load generator. The load profile generation was not the main focus of the study. It is hence not very detailed [5]. In this paper, we will create a more elaborate basis for a mobility load profile generator. To do this, we require a detailed model of processes in households that affect their mobility behaviour. To create household load profiles, there again are various works presenting probabilistic models, evaluating measured data of individual households (bottom up method) [6] or measured

data of accumulated households, e.g. villages, (top down method) [7]. A conceptually quite convincing approach was presented by Pflugradt [8], which, in addition to household load profiles, describes the household's inhabitant's behaviour in detail. This is going to be the basis for our further examinations.

Neither of the e-mobility load profile generators quoted above implements a sophisticated charging regime with regards to battery restrictions. We will incorporate a constant-current-constant-voltage charging algorithm into our simulation design [9]. The temporal resolution of all data is one minute.

HOUSEHOLD LOAD PROFILE GENERATOR BY PFLUGRADT

In his household load profile generator, Pflugradt describes an activity-based model which in itself uses a simulation of "life" within households yielding an activity profile for each member of the household. Such profiles include a selection of 89 activities (fishing, a visit to the museum, shift or office work, yoga lessons, to name a few examples) and for each activity the point in time when the individual starts and finished said activity.

The model is backed by sociological research such as [10] and accounts for a variety of factors including the number of people living in the house, their age and the type of area the household is located in (rural/urban etc.).

The original idea of Pflugradt's work was converting the individual activity profiles to an accumulated power consumption profile for the household. In this work we will use the activity profiles to derive a profile of the household's cars' mobility and later on their charging profiles.

REPORT MOBILITY IN GERMANY AND CLASSIFICATION OF HOUSEHOLD TYPES AND REGIONS

Converting activity behaviour within the household as defined by Pflugradt into mobility behaviour raises additional questions:

1. what kind of area do we simulate and who are the people travelling?
2. does an individual travel to a venue of activity by car, public transport, walk or ride their bicycle?
3. what distance do they travel for this particular activity?

To cover these issues, data from the report Mobility in Germany 2017 (Mobilität in Deutschland 2017) [11] was evaluated and incorporated into the model. The report provides an extensive analysis of the mobility behaviour in Germany.

A demographic and geographic analysis are provided. The report categorises regions by their infrastructure and households by demography:

Types of regions:

1. urban areas:
 - 1.1. metropolitan areas
 - 1.2. large cities
 - 1.3. urbanized areas
 - 1.4. suburbs
2. rural areas:
 - 2.1. town centers
 - 2.2. urbanized areas
 - 2.3. decentral areas

Household types:

1. young households, age < 35 years:
 - 1.1.one-person-household: person 18 - 29 years old
 - 1.2.two-people-household: youngest person 18 - 29 years old
2. senior households, age > 65 years
 - 2.1.one-person-household: person 60 years or older
 - 2.2.two-people- household: youngest person 60 years or older
3. family household with at least one child
 - 3.1.at least one child under 6 years
 - 3.2.at least one child under 14 years
 - 3.3.at least one child under 18 years
 - 3.4.single parent
4. household with only adults
 - 4.1.one-person-household: person 30 - 59 years old
 - 4.2.two-people-household: people 30 - 59 years old

The report provides further statistics based on these classifications which can be used to fill the profile generator with realistic data. A few examples shall be named.

Shares of household types per region are provided (Table 1).

Table 1 : Shares of household types per region

Household type	Region type	1.1	1.2	1.3	1.4	2.1	2.2	2.3
Young households age < 35 years		11 %	11 %	6 %	4 %	6 %	4 %	4 %
Household only adults		36 %	34 %	32 %	31 %	32 %	33 %	36 %
Households in age > 65 years		34 %	37 %	40 %	41 %	45 %	42 %	38 %
Family household, at least one child		18 %	17 %	21 %	23 %	16 %	19 %	22 %

The report also lists percentages of average daily distances travelled broken down to region types (Figure 1):

Figure 1 : Percentages of average daily distances travelled by region type

Yearly average distances travelled for each demographic group were compiled (Figure 2):

Figure 2 : Yearly average distances travelled for each demographic group

The report also contains data on the number of cars for different household types (Table 2):

Table 2 : Numbers of cars for different household types

Region type	Cars per household				average
	none	1	2	3 or more	
1.1	42 %	48 %	9 %	1 %	0.96
1.2	31 %	53 %	15 %	1 %	0.86
1.3	15 %	56 %	25 %	4 %	1.18
1.4	11 %	52 %	31 %	6 %	1.32
2.1	24 %	57 %	17 %	2 %	0.97
2.2	15 %	56 %	24 %	5 %	1.19
2.3	10 %	53 %	30 %	6 %	1.31

As to what means of transportation is used how much, the report presents an analysis as well. The distances travelled by means of transportation are split as follows (Table 3):

Table 3 : Shares of means of transportation

Means of transportation	Share
Car (as driver)	55 %
Car (as passenger)	20 %
Public transport	19 %
Bicycle	3 %
Walking	3 %

Finally, compiling the gathered information and combining it with activity profiles from Pflugradt yields connection profiles: profiles of where cars are located in a power system and when they are connected to their chargers.

An exemplary connection profile is depicted in Figure 3:

Figure 3 : Examples of 'connection profiles' generated by our algorithms

Having obtained our connection profile, we now look into the technical aspect of a e-vehicle charging process: specifications and limits of batteries, chargers and grids.

TECHNICAL ASPECTS: CHARGING CURVES, VEHICLES AND CHARGING STATION TYPES

So far, we were able to solve the sociological aspects of individual e-mobility and create a framework that yields realistic connection profiles for vehicles in a household. As a next step we need to examine two technical aspects to derive actual charging curves from the connection profiles:

1. How does a charging cycle of a state-of-the-art battery work?
2. What types of cars are on the market at the moment and what are the specifications of their batteries and according charging stations?

CCCV-Charging:

Constant Current Constant Voltage or CCCV-charging is a charging algorithm for lithium-ion-batteries that aims at respecting both the battery's maximum charging current and its maximum charging voltage while charging it as quickly as possible. This results in the charging process being divided into two phases: in the first phase, the maximum battery current is the limiting factor, the voltage is continuously adapted to keep the current constantly at its maximum value (CC-phase); in the second phase, after the maximum charging voltage is reached, the current is continuously adapted to maintain the voltage at its maximum level (CV-phase). When the current reaches its minimum value, the charging process is finished. To simulate the cell voltage of the battery as a function of its state of charge, we use the curve depicted in Figure 4 [12]:

Figure 4 : Battery cell voltage as a function of its State of Charge

We now have the information required to formally describe of a CCCV charging process. The charging current can be modelled as

$$I_{charge}(t) = \frac{U_{charge}(t) - U_{cell}}{R_i} \quad (1)$$

$R_{i,cell}$ is the resistance of the battery cell. The cell-voltage U_{cell} is a function of the State of Charge (SOC) of the battery and is based on Figure 4:

$$U_{cell} = f(SOC) \quad (2)$$

In the CC-phase we have

$$I_{charge}(t) = I_{max} \quad (3)$$

and

$$U_{charge}(t) = \frac{I_{max}}{R_{i,cell}} + U_{cell} < U_{max} \quad (4)$$

with a steadily increasing voltage U_{charge} due to the rising SOC of the battery. At some point we reach

$$U_{charge}(t) = U_{max}. \quad (5)$$

From then on, we adapt the charging current I_{charge} to keep U_{charge} at this level, this is the CV-phase:

$$I_{charge}(t) = \frac{U_{max}(t) - U_{cell}}{R_i} \quad (6)$$

Figure 5 depicts currents and voltages for such a charging process:

Figure 5 : CCCV charging curve of a lithium-ion battery

In combination with the specifications for 181 state-of-the-art electric vehicles, hybrid and fully electric, some examples of which are listed in Table 4, we can shape according CCCV-curves.

Table 4 : Market analysis of electric vehicles, 2022 (excerpt)

Manufacturer	Car model	Battery capacity	Max charging power	Consumption per 100 km
Audi	A3 Sportback e-tron	8,8 kWh	22kW	11,4 kWh
Chevrolet	Volt	10,3 kWh	4,6 kW	22,4 kWh
CITROËN	Berlingo Electric	22,5 kWh	3,2 kW	17,7 kWh
Hyundai	Kona Elektro	64 kWh	7,2 kW	14,3 kWh
Mercedes-Benz	B-Klasse B 250 e	28 kWh	11 kW	16,6 kWh
Peugeot	iOn	14,5 kWh	3,7 kW	14,5 kWh
Tesla	Model S 70D	70 kWh	16,5 kW	20 kWh
Toyota	Prius Plug-In Hybrid	4,4 kWh	2,8 kW	7,2 kWh
Volkswagen	e-up!	18,7 kWh	3,6 kW	11,7 kWh
Volvo	C30 Electric	24 kWh	22 kW	17,5 kWh

Data on market shares of certain types of cars could not be found. The car types are thus assumed to be equally distributed, with an option to create a “wealthy neighbourhood” where larger cars are preferred in the distribution (or analogously a less wealthy neighbourhood).

For the simulation solver we add two time-discrete equation to equations (1) through (6):

Firstly, we need an SOC update routine for each discrete simulation time-step.

$$SOC_{t+1} = SOC_t + \frac{U_{charge} \cdot I_{charge}}{C \cdot 1 \text{ min}} \quad (7)$$

After a vehicle returns from an activity, we update the SOC according to equation 7, where cph is the consumption per 100 km of the vehicle, C is the capacitance of its battery, and d is the distance travelled for the activity.

$$SOC_{arrival} = SOC_{start} - \frac{cph \cdot d / (100 \text{ km})}{C} \quad (8)$$

We are now ready to compile the components to a comprehensive load profile generator.

COMPILING THE COMPONENTS

After entering the relevant parameters (simulation duration, region type, share of electric vehicles, optionally the distribution of vehicle types), the activity profiles are generated using Pflugradt’s household profile generator. E-vehicle connection profiles are derived from these, the car types specified and the simulation is executed. Figure 6 depicts the schematic.

Figure 6 : Schematic of the overall profile generation process

IMPLEMENTATION OF A GRID CONTROL ALGORITHM USING THE CONNECTION PROFILE

As a use case for the connection profile in a more complex environment, we apply the CCCV charging regime in our low voltage grid with an additional restriction: a simple P(U)-control is implemented by curtailing charging power. Every minute, in case of a voltage drop below a threshold, the maximum power per charging station is lowered by a certain amount. If the voltage rises above a threshold, the limit is raised. We use a hysteresis of different threshold values to avoid oscillations:

$$\text{if } U_{\min}(t-1) < 0.95 \cdot U_N \text{ then } P_{\max}(t) = P_{\max}(t-1) - 300 \text{ W} \quad (9)$$

$$\text{if } U_{\min}(t-1) > 0.965 \cdot U_N \text{ then } P_{\max}(t) = P_{\max}(t-1) + 300 \text{ W} \quad (10)$$

As a load flow solver, we use the Python-based tool PandaPower [13]. Household load profiles stem from Pflugradts generator, the car charging logic follows the same principles as before except now a curtailment of charging powers by the grid control algorithm is allowed for.

RESULTS

To demonstrate the functionality of the load profile generator, we create a test case and assess the results. In this example, we choose a low voltage grid with the following specifications:

Number of households:	19
Type of region:	rural/urbanized area (2.2)
Electrification rate:	30 %
Neighbourhood type:	average
Simulation duration:	24 hours (noon to noon)

Figure 9 : Charging powers in a 24-hour simulation without voltage controls

In this regime, the minimum voltage magnitude measured across the system over the course of the simulation is as low as 0.83 p.u.

In order to deal with this problematic voltage drop, we implement the P(U)-control regime (equations 9, 10) and simulate again. The resulting charging powers can be found in Figure 10. The global curtailment curve for the charging power is the maximum charging power for all chargers across the system whenever controls are active to make sure voltage limits will not be exceeded.

Figure 10 : Charging powers in a 24-hour simulation with voltage controls

The voltage control curtails the power consumed by the charging stations in times of high demand to protect the grid. Figure 11 depicts the lowest voltage in the system for every simulated minute for both cases.

Figure 11 : Minimum voltage magnitudes across the system without and with voltage controls

The controller's ability to stabilise the grid voltage is well visible, the experiment was successful, as the periods of peak voltage drop were significantly reduced.

CONCLUSION

We were able to combine the existing household activity generator of Pflugradt with a detailed report of the population's mobility behaviour of an industrialised country to an e-mobility load profile generator to be used in low voltage power system simulation. Sociological factors were considered as well as technical factors.

To showcase the functionality of the algorithm, an example simulation was conducted, demonstrating the usefulness of realistic load profiles in an elaborate simulation environment. The initial idea of creating a framework for realistic power system and smart grid simulation including e-mobility was thus successfully implemented.

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NOMENCLATURE

$CCCV$	Constant current constant voltage charging algorithm
cph	Energy consumption per 100 km (e-vehicles)
SOC	Battery State of Charge

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